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PROSE NARRATIVE WISDOM (ON THE EXAMPLE OF ALISHER NAVOI'S GHAZALS)

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Abstract: The article discusses some forms of conveying Alisher Navoi's ghazals to modern readers. In this, mainly, experiences related to the creation of prose narratives of each stanza, lessons and conclusions derived from them are summarized. The author tried to explain his thoughts on the example of a ghazal from the book "Gharayib us-sigar" ("If your anger dies, all my work will be satisfied").

Keywords: Alisher Navoi, gazelle, verse prose, interpretation.

Alisher Navoi's lyrical legacy does not fit within the limits of any world model. Their units of measurement must be completely different. Many years of experience confirm this fact once again. It seems permissible to admit that the researches carried out in recent years fully confirm this thesis.

We will try to explain our thoughts on the example of a ghazal of a thoughtful writer. The text is taken from the writer's book "Gharayib us-sigar". Its full form is as follows:

Қаҳринг ўлса, барча ишимдин малолатдур санга,
Лутфунг ўлса, юз менингдекдин фароғатдур санга.
Эй мени саргаштадин гаҳ фориғу гоҳи малул,
Қаҳринг ул, лутфунг бу, ёрабким, не одатдур санга?
Лутфунг ози жон олур, қаҳринг кўпи ҳам ўлтурур,
Булъажаб ҳоледурур, оё не ҳолатдур санга.
Панд эшитмай севдинг ани, эй кўнгул, чек дарду ранж,
Оздурур ҳар лаҳза гар юз мунча офатдур санга.

Ваҳм эт оҳим ўтидин, эй гулки, даврон боғида
Кўз ёшимдин бу қадар лутфу тароватдур санга.
Эй қуёш, меҳр аҳлини куйдурма бу водийдаким,
Гармравлар оҳидин мунча ҳароратдур санга.
Эй Навоий, истама васл ул қуёшдин заррадек,
Чун неча ул қилса истиғно, ҳақоратдур санга [2.37-38].

The title of the text is not available in the publication, it is provided with a separate title in Navoi's "Commentary of ghazals in the Divan of Gharayib us-sigar". The first line of the first verse of each ghazal is taken into account. Accordingly, this ghazal was given the title "If your anger dies, may all my work be satisfied." It is the 17th ghazal in the collection.

This ghazal was interpreted by candidates of philological sciences, associate professors Olimjon Davlatov and Zuhra Mamadalieva. To make things easier, we bring the prose statements of each bayat side by side:

Қаҳринг ўлса, барча ишимдин малолатдур санга,
Лутфунг ўлса, юз менингдекдин фароғатдур санга.

O. Davlatov	Z. Mamadalieva
When you get angry, you are offended by all my actions. When you are kind, you forget a hundred people like me. [1.189]	If you are angry, you will suffer from all my work (you will not like it), if you give your grace, like me, hundreds of (lovers) will also give you (no harm, only) peace and happiness, that is, you are indifferent to all of us. [1.193]

It is about the relationship between a friend and a lover. According to both scientists, this relationship is "explained" by the language of love. The fact that the words refer to the first person suggests this. In literature, this image is called "lyrical hero". What is clear from his statement is that the same actions of a person can be evaluated in

different ways. This secret industry amazes him. Accordingly, he looks questioningly at his mistress:

Эй мени саргаштадин гаҳ фориғу гоҳи малул,
 Қаҳринг ул, лутфунг бу, ёрабким, не одатдур санга?

O. Davlatov	Z. Mamadalieva
Sometimes you are angry with poor me, sometimes you don't even remember. Where did you get into the habit of showing such anger and kindness?! [1.189]	Oh, I'm a lover who sometimes feels pleasure and sometimes pain from your restless and restless lover, so angry, if your grace is like this, I can't even understand your habit, right?! [1.193]

"Forgiveness" has many meanings. Its meanings as "not subject to others", "free from anything", "indifferent", "ignorant", "at ease" and "calm" [3.418] are recorded in dictionaries. All these qualities belong to the earth. And the lover is just "adventurous". This word has the meanings of "wandering", "wandering", "dangerous", "disturbed", "disappeared" [3.204]. In both prose narratives, the strange situation of the lover is noted.

The surprise continues in the next stanza. Now the focus is on the lack of grace and the abundance of wrath:

Лутфунг ози жон олур, қаҳринг кўпи ҳам ўлтурур,
 Булжажаб ҳоледурур, оё не ҳолатдур санга.

O. Davlatov	Z. Mamadalieva
1. A lot of your anger and a little of your grace will kill a person. How wonderful you are! [1.189]	If there is little of your grace, my soul will be in agony, and if there is too much of your anger, it will kill me. [1.193]

Yor's grace and mercy, and his wrath, are suitable for him. And the lover is tormented by the abundance of the "destiny" of anger, while the grace is less compared to him. The combination of these two qualities in the river creates surprise after surprise.

The path of choice of this lover is simple - he turns to himself, that is, to the soul:

Панд эшитмай севдинг ани, эй кўнгул, чек дарду ранж,
 Оздуруп ҳар лаҳза гар юз мунча офатдур санга.

O. Davlatov	Z. Mamadalieva
1. O heart, you did not listen to advice, you loved him, now bear the pain. Even if such calamities happen every moment, it is not enough for you [1.189].	You were the one who loved him without listening to the advice of the wise (that you should not love and do not suffer), (because of this recklessness) do not suffer pains and hardships, even if at every moment (of love) a hundred times more calamities (from the beginning of love) will be little for you (in fact) [1.193] .

O. Davlatov tries to take into account the formal features of the text. And Z. Mamadalieva makes an additional comment on the text. Accordingly, the first prose account is characterized by its shortness and succinctness, and the next one by its approach.

In the next verse, the form of direct reference to the yor is chosen:

Ваҳм эт оҳим ўтидин, эй гулки, даврон боғида
 Кўз ёшимдин бу қадар лутфу тароватдур санга.

O. Davlatov	Z. Mamadalieva
1. O flower, think of the grass of my heart, that in the garden of Davran, your blooming life will melt because of my shed tears. [1.189]	If you feel peace and happiness from the tears I shed in the garden of this time, oh flower (my beautiful lover who is shining like a flower), be afraid of the fire of my sighs. [1.193]

Proper growth, flowering and survival of a flower in the garden directly depends on the level of water and temperature delivered to it at the time. If this balance is disturbed, there is no question of damage and disaster to the flower in the garden. Therefore, the "herd of woe" that is contrary to the "grace of refreshment" that tears give can destroy all of this. This is now a phenomenon worth panicking about.

Heartburn is not just for lovers. Its manifestation by the mistress has greater power and scope:

Эй қуёш, меҳр аҳлини куйдурма бу водийдаким,

Гармравлар оҳидин мунча ҳароратдур санга.

O. Davlatov	Z. Mamadalieva
1. O sun, do not so burn those who wander in the valley of love. Because the source of your heat is actually the fire of these. [1.189]	O sun (day husnu refreshing beauty), don't burn your lovers in the valley of love (in the fire of your passions and passions), in fact, the heat and temperature on your face is from your fire-breathing lovers. [1.193]

Prose narratives are distinguished by their own interpretations in both. "Garmrav" is a word borrowed from the Persian-Tajik language. It has meanings such as "quick", "speed", "busy". At the same time, this word is also used as a mystical term. Here it means "tax collector", "one who follows the path of religion".

Alisher Navoi made a unique conclusion.

Эй Навоий, истама васл ул қуёшдин заррадек,

Чун неча ул қилса истиғно, ҳақоратдур санга

O. Davlatov	Z. Mamadalieva
O Navoi, even if you are like a particle, do not want the sun. The more its needlessness becomes clear, the more clearly your helplessness and worthlessness will be seen. [1.189]	O Navoi, there is no use in asking for even a speck of visage from that beauty who burns like the sun, (because her feeling towards you is only a tender desire. This) neediness is an insult to you, if you know [1.193].

Both authors sought appropriate ways to convey the content of the verse to the reader.

The meaning of "excuse" is quite broad. It has meanings such as "to be without need", "not to need someone", "to flirt". "Insult" in the modern Uzbek language means kayui. However, in the works of Alisher Navoi, it is used in such meanings as "humiliation" [4.279], "inferiority", "weakness", "impossibility" [4.741].

If you pay attention, the affinities in the general spirit of the prose narratives are more noticeable. Naturally, the main reason for this is the dominant position of the main content reflected in the main text. Nevertheless, in O. Davlatov's comments, there is a desire for brevity, and in Z. Mamadalieva, detail is observed as a result of concern that the comment will be incomprehensible.

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